

Analysis of modern and traditional irrigation technologies at sites in Bangui, Sabon guida and Tounfafi (Tahoua-Niger)

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Abstract

In Niger, faced with persistent climatic hazards that jeopardize primarily rain-fed agricultural production, the development of irrigation has emerged as a promising avenue for securing, increasing, and sustainably expanding agricultural output. However, one of the main constraints to irrigation development is water availability, with irregularity or even a complete lack of water in irrigated areas. Indeed, the main objective of this study is to analyze the performance of modern irrigation technologies used by market gardeners in Bangui, Sabon Gari, and Tounfafi. These new technologies include drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, and irrigation using the Californian network. The traditional irrigation technique is gravity irrigation. The methodological approach we adopted consisted of a literature review, fieldwork, data processing and analysis, followed by interviews using a survey form with producers who practice these modern irrigation technologies. This study reveals that sprinkler irrigation and the Californian irrigation system are the most popular among producers, with over 90% expressing their preference. Finally, the results show that the Californian system is the most widely used and preferred by producers compared to drip irrigation and sprinkler systems. However, further analysis revealed that the sprinkler system is more efficient than the drip irrigation system, which in turn is more efficient than the Californian system.

Introduction

The downward trend in rainfall (successive droughts) observed since the 1970s in most of the Sahel region, along with high population density and the degradation of natural resources (declining soil fertility), has resulted in reduced agricultural production. These factors have strongly argued in favor of adopting irrigation as a priority strategy for agricultural development. Increasing agricultural productivity also depends on developing irrigation, which is a means of intensifying agriculture. Indeed, irrigation can double or even quadruple yields and lift beneficiary populations above the poverty line (FAO, 1994). Therefore, modern irrigation technologies must employ rational techniques and principles that allow for the efficient use of water and optimize irrigation in relation to all other essential agricultural inputs and operations. These modern irrigation technologies are therefore being implemented in irrigation; among them are drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, and the Californian system. In theory, these techniques allow for application efficiencies of around 90%, compared to 60% for the best-managed traditional systems (Tiercelin 2006; Bisconer 2010; Darouich et al. 2012; Wanvoeke et al. 2016), yields (Garb and Friedlander 2014; Chandran and Surendran 2015), and economic profitability (Rodrigues et al. 2013; Darouich et al. 2014). The general objective of this study is to analyze modern irrigation technologies and those of the traditional gravity irrigation system used for thousands of years.

2. Matériel and Methods

2.1 Material

✓ Presentation of the study area

Figure 1: Map of the rural commune of Madaoua with the study areas

The materials used to conduct this study are:

- a motorcycle for transportation;
- a survey form;
- a camera for taking photographs.

2.2 Methods

To achieve the objectives set out in this study, the following methodological approach was adopted.

Field Data Collection

This field research phase is limited not only to living alongside the various agricultural producers but also to conducting physical monitoring in the field. In addition to these defined activities, data collection related to the fieldwork was carried out using several methods.

- Conversations with producers aimed at studying and gathering as much information as possible, including their perspectives, to better understand the extent of their impact and the difficulties they encounter in implementing modern irrigation technologies. These conversations are subdivided into two categories:

- First category: group and individual conversations

- Group conversations with producers were chosen to gather general information and determine whether the producers in question have a good understanding of modern irrigation technologies;

- Based on this, individual conversations with producers, including questions, were conducted to understand whether or not they were actually using modern irrigation technologies.

- Second category: Conversations with technical services

These conversations were conducted solely by the technical services of the various intervention sites. The purpose of these conversations was to determine whether producers using modern irrigation technologies were contacting the technical services to monitor the maintenance and proper functioning of these technologies.

*Field observations: Accompanied by the producers and sometimes by village chiefs, we conducted regular and valuable field visits.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results

3.1.1 Identification and characterization of modern irrigation technologies at the intervention sites.

Based on extensive fieldwork, it was found that vegetable growers at the various intervention sites used only one modern irrigation technique out of three systems (drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, and the Californian system). The Californian system was the most popular among growers because it reduces water loss on sandy soils and thus improves irrigation efficiency.

Next, this Californian system is characterized by buried pipes. The network is installed using various connecting pieces and other essential components.

3.1.2 Inventory of modern irrigation technologies in the intervention areas

Table 1 shows the reasons why producers in the study areas chose modern irrigation technologies.

Table 1: Reasons for producers choosing modern irrigation technologies in the study areas

Reason for choice	Houra	Koumassa	Roumbouki	S Guida	Tajaye	Tounfafi	Zourdi	Chi-square test	V-rs	Meaning
Effectiveness	24,4	33,3	40,0	20,0	20,0	22,7	20,0	17,5	60,0	**
Ease of use	2,2				20,0	9,1		2,5		*
Efficiency	73,3	66,7	60,0	80,0	60,0	68,2	80,0	80,0	40,0	***

The chi-square test results show that 17.5% of farmers use modern irrigation technologies for their effectiveness; while 2.5% use them for their ease of use, and 80% use them for their efficiency (reduced water losses).

Table 2 shows the preferred times for farmers to use modern irrigation technologies.

Table 2: Degree of use of the California Network and gravity irrigation systems by farmers at the study sites

Irrigation system	Houra	Koumassa	Roumbouki	Sabon Guida	Tajaé	Tounfafi	Zourdi	Chi-square test	V-crs	Meaning
Gravity System	26,7	-	40,0	-	-	2,3	20,0	60,0	40,0	**
Californian	73,3	100,0	60,0	100,0	100,0	97,7	80,0	40,0	60,0	***

The results across all intervention sites show that 60% of producers in the target population use traditional irrigation technology, while 40% use modern irrigation technology (specifically, the Californian system).

Table 3 illustrates the problems encountered by producers using the Californian system at the study sites.

Table 3: Problems encountered by producers using the Californian system at the study sites

Existence of a problem	Houra	Koumassa	Roumbouki	SGuida	Tajaye	Tounfafi	Zourdi	Chi-square test	V-rs	Meaning
Yes	13,3	-	20,0	20,0	-	4,5	-	17,5	20,0	**
No	86,7	100,0	80,0	80,0	100,0	95,5	100,0	82,5	80,0	***

The results show that 17.5% of producers using the new irrigation technology experienced problems, while 82.5% of producers using the modern irrigation technology did not.

Table 4 shows the relative positive change observed by producers at the study sites following the use of modern irrigation technology compared to the gravity system.

Table 4: Positive change by producers of modern irrigation technologies compared to the gravity system.

Existence of Change	Houra	Koumassa	Roumbouki	Sabon Guida	Tajaé	Tounfafi	Zourdi	Chi-square test	V-rs	Meaning
Yes	31,1	16,7	40,0	20,0	40,0	27,3	20,0	72,5	40,0	**
No	68,9	83,3	60,0	80,0	60,0	72,7	80,0	27,5	60,0	***

The results across all intervention sites show that 72.5% of producers noticed a change when using the new technology, while 27.7% did not notice any change.

Table 5 shows the performance of irrigation systems according to the vegetable producers surveyed at the study sites.

Table 5: Performance of irrigation systems according to the vegetable producers surveyed at the study sites

Irrigation System	Houra	Koumassa	Roumbouki	Sabon Guida	Tajaé	Tounfafi	Zourdi	Chi-square test	V-rs	Meaning
Gravity System	11,1	-	20,0	-	-	-	20,0	-	40,0	**
Drip Irrigation System	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,0		ns
Sprinkler Irrigation System	17,8	33,3	20,0	20,0	40,0	25,0		25,0	20,0	*
California	71,1	66,7	60,0	80,0	60,0	75,0	80,0	70,0	40,0	**

ns : not significant

*= Significant

**= Very significant

***= Very very significant

The chi-square test results show that 5% of producers perceived a change in labor requirements, 25% perceived a change in yield, and 70% perceived an improvement in irrigation efficiency.

Table 6 shows the impacts of modern drip irrigation technology on crops grown at the study sites in the intervention areas.

Table 6: Impacts of Modern Drip Irrigation Technology on Crops Grown at the Study Sites

Irrigation System	Houra	Koumassa	Roumbouki	Sabon Guida	Tajaye	Tounfafi	Zourdi	Chi-square test	V-rs	Meaning
Gravity System	6,7	-	-	20,0	-	4,5	-	7,5	-	ns
Drip Irrigation System	93,3	100,0	100,0	80,0	100,0	95,5	100,0	92,5	100,0	***

The chi-square test results show that 7.5% of producers are convinced that the use of this new technology will have an impact, while 92.5% are not convinced that its use will have no impact on their farming practices.

Table 7 shows the different water supply sources at the study sites.

Table 7: Types of irrigation systems that producers would like to obtain at the study sites

Irrigation System	Houra	Koumassa	Roumbouki	SGuida	Tajaye	Tounfafi	Zourdi	Test Khi- d	V-rs	Meaning
Gravity System	22,2	-	-	-	20,0	20,5	-	10,0	-	ns
Drip Irrigation System	77,8	100,0	100,0	100,0	80,0	79,5	100,0	90,0	100,0	***

The results show that 10% of producers wanted to have a drip irrigation system installed and 90% of producers wanted to have a sprinkler system installed.

3.2 Discussion

This study highlights that market garden producers in the Madaoua department in general, and in particular those in the commune of Bangui, Sabon Guida and the village of Tounfafi, use three modern irrigation technologies: sprinkler irrigation, drip irrigation and the Californian system, and the traditional system (gravity system).

The reasons given by farmers at the study sites for choosing modern irrigation technologies were effectiveness (17.5%), ease of use (2.5%), and efficiency (80%). These results corroborate the work of Andreas (2002) and Levidow (2014), who indicated that irrigators' choices of modern irrigation technologies were primarily based on effectiveness and efficiency. The efficiency of drip irrigation is also confirmed by several other studies (Caswell et al. in 1990, Zellal and Smadhi in 2007). A comparative study of three modern irrigation technologies (Californian, drip irrigation, and sprinkler irrigation) conducted in Burkina Faso by Adolphe(2018) revealed a variation in water requirements between the three technologies, with this variation being 50% between the Californian system and the sprinkler system. Therefore, the drip irrigation system is the best modern irrigation technology in terms of network efficiency.

Furthermore, drip irrigation is a very efficient system (FAO, 2008). Indeed, impacts of modern drip irrigation technology (D&I) on crops were observed at the study sites (7.5%). Our results do not align with those obtained in Ghana by Adeoti (2009). His work showed that over 60% of irrigators observed significant impacts on crops. This difference is likely due to the fact that the implementation of drip irrigation was not sustained at our various study sites. Regarding positive changes, across all study sites, 72.5% of producers reported a significant improvement when using modern irrigation technologies. Albaji (2015) obtained similar results. According to the author, following his investigations, over 80% of irrigators observed a significant improvement through the use of modern irrigation technologies, particularly drip irrigation and sprinkler irrigation. In view of all the above, the results show that among the modern irrigation systems we have studied, drip irrigation and sprinkler irrigation are more efficient compared to the Californian system, although it is the most appropriate for the Nigerian context, which is not comfortable for our context, more specifically my follow-up interventions, including the Californian system (Salia., 2011). Despite the performance and positive perception of these two modern techniques, irrigators complain about their high costs and the lack of technical expertise required to operate them. Our results are similar to those obtained by Laurenda et al. (2015), who showed that the most widely used modern irrigation technologies by farmers are drip irrigation and sprinkler irrigation due to their cost-effectiveness. These authors emphasize that the only constraints faced by irrigators are the high cost of these technologies and the difficulty in mastering their technical aspects.

Conclusion

Water resources are currently under pressure in many regions of the world. Irrigated agriculture, the primary consumer of water, is therefore receiving increasing attention. This is why the present study analyzes modern irrigation technologies in the Madaoua department, focusing on the communes of Bangui, Sabon Guida, and the village of Tounfafi. Thus, according to this study, the Californian system is the most suitable and widely used by vegetable growers at the study sites, compared to drip irrigation and sprinkler systems. Indeed, the analysis of these three irrigation systems shows that sprinkler irrigation is less efficient than drip irrigation. This sprinkler irrigation system is more efficient compared to the Californian system. To contribute to this debate, this work focuses primarily on the effectiveness and efficiency of these new technologies in terms of their impact on water resources, but also from a broader perspective that incorporates the diverse concerns of irrigators.

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